

Can 280 Characters Speak for Researchers? Leveraging Twitter Data for Unobtrusive Measurement of Academics' Well-Being

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ABSTRACT

Understanding and promoting researchers' well-being is crucial for achieving successful research outcomes and fostering a thriving scientific community. While conventional well-being assessments can be resource-intensive, social media language analysis offers a promising solution. This research-in-progress aims to evaluate the potential of Twitter (now "X") data in providing insights into researchers' well-being. To address this research question, we will derive researchers' well-being from our available Twitter dataset and use survey data on a known event (i.e., initial phase of the COVID-19 pandemic) for external validation of our results. By assessing the eligibility of data from academic social networks as a well-being indicator for researchers, we aim to lay the groundwork for real-time monitoring for informed decision-making and foster a supportive research environment.

KEYWORDS

unobtrusive measurement; scholarly communication; researcher characteristics; Twitter; student submission

INTRODUCTION

Researchers' well-being significantly influences various aspects, including work performance, productivity, work climate, health, and the attractiveness of research as a career path (Boehm & Lyubomirsky, 2008; Dimaria et al., 2020; Howell et al., 2007; Torrasi, 2013). Understanding and promoting researcher well-being are vital for successful long-term research outcomes, a supportive research culture, and a thriving scientific community. While conventional well-being assessments (e.g., Diener et al., 1985; Watson et al., 1988) rely on time- and money-consuming surveys, social media language analysis offers a potential solution for large-scale and unobtrusive well-being assessment (for a review, see Sametoğlu et al., 2023). This approach offers the advantages that the data are not altered by experimental biases like questioning or hindsight bias, and can arise and be collected automatically and continuously. Jaidka and colleagues (2020) have demonstrated the accurate and robust unobtrusive measurement of well-being using Twitter (now called "X") data. However, it is an open question whether Twitter data can serve as an accurate indicator of researcher well-being. The distinctive ways in which researchers might employ Twitter, characterized by greater professionalism and emotional distance compared to the general population, introduce complexities that demand careful consideration. Therefore, our research question is:

Can Twitter data be used to gain insights into the well-being of the psychological research community?

EVALUATION AND HYPOTHESES

To address this research question and evaluate the approach for researchers, we will derive researchers' well-being from their tweets. Then, analogous to Evans (2014), we use survey data on a known event (i. e., initial phase of the COVID-19 pandemic) for external validation of our results. The pandemic had a known impact on academic life and well-being (e.g., Alfawaz et al., 2021; KNAW, 2022; LNVH, 2021; Ramos, 2021; Subramanya et al., 2020). Hence, we expect to find this trend in our results if signals of well-being can be detected in scientific communication on Twitter at all.

H1: Well-being derived from tweets are lower for the period during the COVID-19 pandemic than before the pandemic.

Additionally, the literature suggests that especially female researchers (e.g., Harper et al., 2020; Izquierdo-Useros et al., 2022; KNAW, 2022; Sohrabi et al., 2021) suffered more from the effects of the pandemic. This should also be reflected in the insights we gain from assessing well-being from Twitter data.

H2: The effect (H1) is stronger for female researchers.

METHODS

Data

We analyzed a dataset of a previous study (Müller et al., 2023), which comprises Twitter data from 15,987 psychology researchers, including profile descriptions, tweets, and metadata such as time stamps and references (tweet as a response to another tweet). To gather this dataset, we had developed an identification algorithm that crawls the mentions network of a seed dataset of verified psychological researchers and classifies accounts via

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keyword matching in their profile descriptions. With this approach we were able to identify psychological researchers on Twitter that disclose themselves as such. For the current study, we excluded all non-english tweets and tweets without self-disclosure (i.e., retweets and “informational” tweets for a new paper or an open position).

Operationalization of Well-Being

The psychological construct of well-being lacks a consistent definition in the literature. Nevertheless, it is commonly categorized into three components: emotional (affect/valence), cognitive (evaluation of one's life), and eudaimonic (meaning in life) dimensions (e.g., Das et al., 2020; Willroth, 2022; Yang & Srinivasan, 2016). Notably, many studies exclude the eudaimonic aspect and predominantly focus on the emotional component (Luhmann, 2017).

For *emotional* well-being, we conducted a sentiment analysis of the tweets analogous to Jaidka et al. (2020), leveraging a pre-trained roBERTa-base language model (i.e., TimeLM-22, Luoreiro et al., 2022) for our present study as the main analytical focus. Since we only have researchers in our dataset who disclose themselves as such, we assume that the corresponding accounts are predominantly used in this function. Given this work context, we will assess *cognitive* well-being through job satisfaction rather than life satisfaction (in progress at the time of writing). Building upon the approach of Schwartz et al. (2013), we will try to gain insights into the cognitive component of occupational well-being by analyzing how researchers refer to well-being-related topics (cf. PERMA+4 dimensions; Donaldson et al., 2022). For this purpose, semi-supervised topic modeling (BERTopic; Grootendorst, 2022) is used to determine whether positive or negative tweets are made related to the respective topic.

Analysis

For the main analysis (emotional well-being) we compared the sentiment scores in the year before the pandemic with those in the first year of the pandemic. We aggregated the results per week to create the two metric outcomes (a) mean of positive and (b) of negative sentiment scores per week. For the exploratory analysis (cognitive well-being), the categorical outcome will also be aggregated over a period of time, resulting in the two outcomes (a) sum of tweets that positively and (b) negatively mention well-being related topics. For both, a Structural Break Analysis for interrupted time series is performed.

PRELIMINARY RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Analysis of H1 suggests that well-being trends observed during the COVID-19 pandemic are evident in researchers' Twitter data, primarily on a descriptive level. However, inferential statistical validation of pandemic-related well-being impacts is inconclusive. The pandemic's influence on positive sentiments was statistically significant, while its effect on negative sentiments remained primarily descriptive. Since both shifts must attain significance to accept H1, it cannot be supported. At the time of writing, analysis of H2 and exploratory analysis of cognitive well-being are pending.

The preliminary results indicate that emotional well-being can be inferred from tweets – at least in terms of positive sentiments. Further analyses revealed a strong effect of the January 6 United States Capitol attack on both types of sentiments at that time. This raises the question of whether and to what extent specific events outside academia affect researchers' well-being and ultimately their professional work. Moreover, it remains an open question whether the current findings focusing on psychology researchers can be generalized to the scientific community as a whole.

Our approach of utilizing Twitter data to gain insights into well-being yielded promising results, yet they must be taken with a grain of salt: First, the future of using Twitter/X for research seems bleak due to the termination of free academic access. However, the presented approach is not limited to Twitter and could be adapted to other language-based social media platforms commonly used by researchers (e.g., Mastodon, LinkedIn, or other emerging platforms). In any case, continuous access to the digital scholarly communication of researchers would be paramount. Second, we focused on the period around the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic. While this comes in handy as a means of external validation of the well-being shift due to the long lasting effects of the pandemic, future research should focus on other periods in time and accompany the described unintrusive approach with survey data. By doing so, potential covariates (such as external events) could be probed via questionnaires.

Whether automated real-time monitoring of well-being can be enabled on a collective level is still to be answered, although our results are encouraging. This could have profound implications for policy-makers, as continuous longitudinal well-being data could aid in identifying problems early and making informed decisions to foster a thriving scientific community. Ultimately, this could contribute to sustainable progress and knowledge gain in science in the long term. Moreover, understanding and addressing factors that affect scientists' mental health and job satisfaction can enhance collaboration, communication, and overall team cohesion. Additionally, prioritizing scientists' well-being fosters a supportive and nurturing environment that can lead to increased creativity and innovation.

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